

PRODUCTION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS BY POWDER PREPREGGING

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ABSTRACT

A dry powder continuous fiber composite prepregging process has been developed which produces a material suitable for composite manufacturing operations. Experiments conducted with a laboratory prototype have shown that the process produces a uniformly deposited particulate coating on individual fibers at speeds of at least 2 cm/sec and with matrix volume fractions controllable over a wide range with little variation. Economic analysis of the process coupled with reasonable extrapolation to larger capacities shows that the non-material manufacturing costs associated with using this process are at \$1.00 per pound of prepreg produced at quantities of 25,000 pounds per year. The materials and engineering analysis of the process indicate that it can be applied to both thermoplastic and thermoset matrices.

KEYWORDS: Powder; Prepreg; Composite; Manufacturing; Process

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic matrices and high temperature thermoset matrices have been produced and have great potential but their use has been limited by the lack of good processing techniques to make flexible prepreg tapes. The general intractability of these matrices due to their high viscosity and high processing temperatures gives rise to a host of problems such as the manufacture of stiff and boardy tape, solution devolatilization leading to the formation of voids with its attendant loss in mechanical properties and prepreg tapes with high resin content. A review of the literature has shown that there are many alternative methods that can be used for prepregging.

2. BACKGROUND

Different methods have been employed in the past to make composite prepreg.

(a) Solution Processing. Thermoplastic polymer is dissolved in a solvent and the fiber tow is impregnated with the resulting low viscosity solution¹. The solvent must be completely removed to avoid void generation during composite consolidation. The solubility of the polymer also indicates that it will be prone to solvent attack. A major limitation is that some polymers are not soluble in solvents.

(b) Slurry Processing. The fiber tow is passed through a slurry tank which contains

polymer particles suspended in a liquid carrier. Taylor² outlines a process whereby the particles are suspended in water thickened with a material such as polyethylene oxide to increase the viscosity to 40-300 Pa·s at 25°C. O'Connor³, in a very thorough discussion in a patent points out potential problems which include finding the right concentration of slurry, maintaining the optimum concentration in the resin tank and accumulation of excess resin at the die entrance (where the impregnated tow is consolidated into a tape or flat sheet). The minimum void content in the slurry-processed tapes were about 2-4%. Dyksterhouse et. al.⁴ impregnate fibers in an impregnation bath filled with a polymer binder in which the polymer particles are uniformly suspended. The gelled binder has plastic flow characteristics and shear-thinning behavior.

(c) Melt Impregnation. In this method, the fiber roving is impregnated with molten polymer. Two approaches have been used to accomplish this - (a) A crosshead extruder feeds molten polymer into a die through which the rovings pass⁵, and, (b) the fibers pass through a molten resin bath fitted with impregnation pins to increase the permeability of the polymer into the tow. The impregnation pins can be heated to decrease viscosity locally to further improve the impregnation process⁶. In either case, the forces exerted on the fibers e.g. from the die pressure for the crosshead extruder are extremely high and may cause fiber damage. The resulting prepreg usually lacks tack and drape.

(d) Film Stacking. Layers of fiber reinforcement either in the form of unidirectional tows or woven fabrics are stacked with thermoplastic sheets and consolidated under pressure for long times⁷. This method is widely used due to the relative ease of manufacture. Disadvantages include high resin content, the uneconomic (labor-intensive) nature of the process and difficulty in impregnating the fiber tow (high pressure forces the fibers together) with high viscosity matrix material.

(e) Fiber Co-mingling. The thermoplastic matrix is spun into a fine yarn and co-mingled with the reinforcing fiber tow to produce a co-mingled hybrid yarn⁸. These hybrid yarns can be consolidated to form composite parts. An advantage of this technique is the drapeability of the hybrid yarn while the high cost involved in producing thermoplastic yarn and weaving it with the reinforcing fibers is an obvious disadvantage.

(f) Dry Powder Impregnation. Dry thermoplastic powder is introduced into a fiber tow which is processed by heating to sinter the powder particles onto the fibers. This technique was first employed by Price⁹ who passed glass roving through a bed (either fluidized or loosely packed) of thermoplastic powder. The particles stick to the fibers due to electrostatic attraction. The tow is then heated and passed through a die to produce an impregnated tow. The impregnation is macroscopic, i.e. the particles coat clusters of fibers rather than individual fibers and is targeted mainly at producing short-fiber reinforced thermoplastics. Polypropylene particles with an average diameter of 250 microns were used. Ganga¹⁰, fluidized particles less than 20 microns in size in a fluidization chamber, impregnated glass rovings and then covered this with an outer sheath of a second material of lower melting point than the impregnated particles. The second sheath was extruded onto the tow. Muzzy¹¹ demonstrated the ability to manufacture prepreg by passing a spread tow through an high voltage electrostatic fluidized bed of powder (>50 microns). Allen et. al.¹² impregnated the fibers in a recirculating chamber with annular walls to aid in powder recovery and a fan at the bottom to disperse thermoplastic particles (5-20 microns).

3. PROCESS DESCRIPTION

A new alternative dry powder process has been developed which is based on a design of a prepregging process which incorporates the components shown in Figure 1¹³. The fiber tow is unwound from a fiber spool and passes through a device (spreader) which spreads the collimated fiber tow (or tows) to any desired width. A pretreatment tank may be used to modify the fiber surface to provide better adhesion with the thermoplastic matrix or to apply a binder on the fibers. The spread tow enters the impregnation chamber where it meets a controlled concentration of

particles. At this position, the means of adhering the particles to the fibers is either electrostatic attraction or through the use of a binder on the fiber surface. The impregnated tow passes through a heater where the particles are "fixed" on the fiber surface with the help of thermal energy. The resulting flexible tape is then wound on a takeup drum.

The advantages of this process are:

(i) The average particle size of the matrix is approximately equal to the dimensions of the fiber for optimum impregnation. Impregnation of individual fibers becomes more difficult with larger particle size resulting in an uneven coating and/or a resin-rich composite. The level of precise control over fiber-matrix volume fractions that can be achieved decreases with increasing particle size.

(ii) The fiber tow can be spread out to a sufficient width so that each fiber in the tow is uniformly coated with particles.

(iii) The concentration of powder particles in the "impregnation chamber" where the particles meet the fibers is constant and controllable at all times. This facilitates the manufacture of high quality prepreg tapes in a wide range of volume fractions.

(iv) The mechanism of adhering the particles to the fibers is controllable and well-understood.

(v) The resulting prepreg tape is flexible so that complex parts can be formed easily by consolidation.

4. FORMATION OF THE PREPREG TAPE

Tape manufacture by the powder prepregging process involves (1) spreading of the fiber tow and its uniform impregnation by fine particles and (2) coalescence of the particles on the fibers to form a prepreg tape.

4.1 Spreading of the Fiber Tow The function of the spreader is to ensure that the fiber tow is spread to a width large enough to expose individual fibers so that powder impregnation occurs throughout the fiber tow. The process of spreading should also be gentle enough so that critical sized flaws or abrasion damage that reduce reinforcing fiber strength are not induced in the fibers. Various commercial methods are available, such as directed air streams. An alternative method which is very efficient in spreading the fiber tow to its full one-fiber thick geometric width has been developed and is the subject of a patent application.

4.2 Impregnation of the Fiber Tow The impregnation chamber has been designed such that it delivers a controlled concentration of particles to the fibers at all times. This is essential in order to manufacture prepreg tapes of any desired volume fraction with a minimum standard deviation. Fine control over the impregnation process is achieved with particle sizes approximately equal to the fiber diameter. However, the fluidization of fine particles less than 20-30 microns in diameter is complicated by the presence of interparticle forces. Van der Waal's forces act over a distance of 100 Angstroms and interparticle distances in a packed bed at the point of contact are of the order of 5 Angstroms¹⁴. This leads to particle agglomeration and channeling when fine particles are fluidized in a conventional bed^{15 16}. In addition, particles tend to acquire charge by frictional or sliding contact through a process known as contact electrification or triboelectrification¹⁷. Fine particles tend to charge negatively and if there is a broad particle size distribution, there may be a change in particle charge with decreasing particle size. Polymer particles also tend to charge readily and retain a charge for long times because they have high values of electrical resistivity and low electrical permittivity. This tribocharging is the primary mechanism responsible for the attraction of fine polymer particles to graphite fibers. Imposed external means of electrostatic enhancement of particle charge requiring the use of separate electrostatic generating equipment is not required because the triboelectric effect is sufficiently large to cause strong adhesion of the particles to fiber surfaces on contact.

4.3 Coalescence The impregnated fiber tow enters the heater immediately after the impregnation step to permanently fix the particles to the reinforcing fiber. A sequence of events can occur in the heater (Figure 2) in which the particles are heated to their sintering point, interparticle sintering takes place between adjacent particles, a film forms on the fiber surface and finally the formation of a stable configuration of axisymmetric or non-symmetric droplets. A process control model has been developed which includes consideration of heat transfer, sintering, and film and droplet forming mechanisms.

4.3.1 Heat transfer. The temperature of the powder-impregnated fiber tow is raised by convection and radiation to a value greater than the melting or softening point of the polymer particles. The physical situation is shown in Figure 3. Individual impregnated fibers or clusters of impregnated fibers pass through the heater as a flat porous sheet. The Biot number which measures the significance of internal heat conduction within the solid to external heat convection to the surface of the solid is very low for this system indicating that an external lumped model is applicable to this system. For a lumped system of mass m , specific heat C_p , surface area A , heat transfer coefficient (which includes contributions from convection and radiation) h , the time t required to raise its temperature from T_a (ambient temperature) to T when the temperature of the heater is T_h is given by

$$t = \frac{mC_p}{hA} \ln \frac{(T_h - T_a)}{(T_h - T)}$$

Lower and upper bounds can be calculated by considering an isolated particle in a convective medium and a large-diameter cluster of coated fibers respectively.

4.3.2 Interparticle sintering. Adjacent particles begin to sinter i.e. a neck forms between neighboring particles and grows until the particles coalesce into one as reported by Frenkel¹⁸. The work required for a change in shape is equated to a decrease in surface energy. Viscous flow dissipation accounts for the work done during coalescence.

$$\frac{x^2}{r} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\gamma}{\mu} t$$

Where x is the radius of the interparticle bridge, r is the radius of the particle, γ is the polymer melt surface tension, μ is the polymer viscosity and t is the sintering time.

Frenkel's theory can be used to predict the sintering times for some engineering thermoplastics of interest in structural applications. The surface tension in all the cases is assumed to be 30 dynes/cm. As can be seen from the results in Table 1, an increase in either particle size or viscosity would serve to increase sintering times.

4.3.3 Film and Droplet Formation. Interparticle sintering carried to its full conclusion leads to the formation of a film which breaks up to form droplets on the fiber. These droplets are of varying shape and symmetry with respect to the fiber axis. The shape of these droplets changes with time to an equilibrium configuration which can be axisymmetric or non-symmetric depending on droplet volume and the influence of gravitational forces^{19 20}. In the case of a spread fiber tow in which the impregnated fibers are in intermittent contact with each other, capillary forces between adjacent fibers may make film formation thermodynamically favorable. The final configuration depends on interfiber distances and droplet sizes in addition to surface tension forces.

Table 1. Polymer Particle Sintering Times as a Function of Particle Size

Polymer	Nylon 12	PEEK	PPS	PEI	PS
Processing Temp. (°C)	215	390	315	350	350
Melt Viscosity (Pa·s)	33	3500	2500	2000	2000
Particle Size	Sintering Times (seconds)				
10 microns	<0.004	<0.39	<0.30	0.22	0.22
100 microns	<0.04	<3.90	<3.0	2.22	2.22
250 microns	<0.18	<9.72	<6.94	5.56	5.56

4.3.5. Consolidation. The powder-impregnated prepreg tapes are consolidated under heat and pressure to form void-free composite parts. If the impregnation of particles in the fiber tow is uniform, this leads to the formation of uniform-sized droplets and a polymer sheath on the fibers. The phenomenon of consolidation involves two steps - (i) Intimate contact at the polymer-polymer interface at numerous sites across the composite and (ii) autohesion or the interdiffusion of polymer chains across the interface to cause the interface to disappear. Consolidation is usually performed at temperatures higher than the melt temperature for semi-crystalline or the softening point for amorphous thermoplastic polymers. Physical deformation at the polymer-polymer interface is required to achieve intimate contact.

The design of optimum consolidation cycles for powder-impregnated thermoplastic and thermoset composites involves the selection of time, temperature, pressure and cooling rates (for semi-crystalline materials). Powder-impregnated thermoplastic tapes may require long contact times to ensure that intimate contact has been achieved but thermoset matrix tape processing has to balance the reactivity against the impregnation time. Another variable which comes into play is the volume fraction of matrix in the composite. The saturation pressure increases with decreasing matrix volume fraction (time and temperature constant) due to the ability of the fibers to store elastic energy during consolidation.

5. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

5.1 Materials. The fiber and the matrix have to be characterized for their properties in order to optimize processing. These properties include particle size, fiber diameter, charge-to-mass ratio of the particles, electrical conductivity of the fiber, interparticle cohesive forces, matrix viscosity, crystallinity, transition temperatures, fiber-matrix thermal properties and surface energies. For the demonstration of this process, a polyamide powder (nylon-12) and a graphite fiber (AS-4, 3K tow) were selected as appropriate for the laboratory scale prototype. The 3K tow has the added benefit of being a size suitable for subsequent textile operations. The material properties of importance for these constituents are listed in Table 2.

5.2 Process Evaluation

5.2.1 Prepreg Matrix Content. An experimental program²¹ was conducted to test evaluate the operating conditions of this process with the fiber (Hercules AS-4 carbon fibers, 3000 fibers/tow) and matrix described. With the fiber tow initially spread to a width of 5-15 cm and the system operating at about 2 cm/sec for periods of about one hour, duplicate runs at constant conditions were made to test the reproducibility of the process. The evaluation criterion was the volume fraction of matrix picked up by measuring tape aliquots of 35 second duration (about 0.7 meters).

The experiments were then repeated at different aerosolizer conditions to vary the volume fraction of matrix that could be produced over a wide range. Table 3 lists the results of these runs.

Table 2. Contituent Material Properties

Property	Polyamide	AS4 Carbon Fiber
Particle Size (microns)	9.2	8.0
Specific Gravity	1.02	1.8
Melt Temp. (°C)	175°	---
Specific Heat (cal/gm/°C)	0.58-0.81	0.22-0.27
Thermal Conduct.(W/M/°C)	0.22-0.31	5.73
Viscosity (Pa·s)	52.6	---
Surface Tension (mJ/M ²)	0.30	---

Table 3. Results of Prepregging Experiments

Run Time (minutes)	Tow Speed (cm/s)	Matrix Volume Fraction (%)
60	1.94	9.9 ± 3
58	2.09	20.5 ± 3
60	1.96	32.3 ± 3
60	1.94	44.1 ± 3
40	1.94	52.9 ± 3

5.2.2 Matrix Particle Coalescence. The sintering and coalescence of the polyamide particles on carbon fibers was studied with the help of a specially designed hot stage which mounts under an optical microscope. Experiments consist of mounting a single fiber or a spread tow coated with powder particles on a frame. This frame was placed inside the hot stage which is maintained at the heater temperature. The coalescence events are either observed visually or videotaped for further analysis.

The prepreg tapes made by the process show a tendency to cluster in bundles in the heater. These bundles are roughly cylindrical and the times taken for cylindrical objects to heat up convectively can be calculated. The h values were estimated from empirical correlations²² and Table 3 summarizes the calculated times for clusters of different sizes to raise their temperature from ambient (21°C) to 180°C. The time taken for heat transfer increases with increasing cluster diameter. Cluster sizes for the prepreg tapes made by the process are usually within 100 microns. This analysis clearly demonstrates the advantages of generating well-spread tows to reduce heating requirements and to increase tow velocities of the prepreg tapes. Interparticle sintering that leads to film formation occurs in less than one second (when the heater temperature T_h is 215°C) for the polyamide particles used in this investigation from experimental observation. This confirms the prediction by Frenkel's theory.

From the standpoint of high quality prepreg tapes, uniform impregnation of particles in the

spread tow leads to interparticle sintering and coalescence into a uniform film. Thermodynamic instability forces the film to break up into droplets which equilibrate with each other through transport along a polymer sheath resulting in uniform-sized droplets along the fiber axis. If the fibers are clustered together, capillarity will favor film formation between adjacent fibers. Large diameter clusters which are caused by poor spreading tend to reduce the flexibility of the prepreg tape. The residence time of the powder-impregnated tow in the heater is the time required for the coalescence phenomena to occur. The optimum residence time is a function of temperature (which primarily influences viscosity and therefore sintering and spreading times) and the mass of particles picked up by the fiber tow during the impregnation step.

Further investigations are underway to study coalescence phenomena as a function of temperature, viscosity, particle size for this material and other engineering thermoplastics. This will help predict optimum residence times in the heater which in turn will influence the tow velocity through the entire process.

6. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

In order to evaluate this process as to its economic competitiveness in the composite prepregging arena, an economic analysis has been made. Since the process as proposed would be applicable to any fiber-matrix combination, the model and analysis concentrated on the manufacturing costs alone. A comparison was also made between the costs associated with preparing prepreg with the laboratory prototype which are expected to be expensive and with a "scaled-up" version of the process.

The parameters used to evaluate the current system were:

The capital costs are fixed at duplicating the current system which includes the spreader, aerosolizer, sintering oven and associated computer driven control system. The current costs plus a 20% increase were used to insure conservatism in the estimate. Straight line depreciation over ten years was used to amortize the capital costs.

The labor rate of \$20 per hour was used for all operators of the system. A tow speed of 10 cm/second for three simultaneous tows was used as the basis for determining all costs. All costs were then converted into pounds per hour of material produced so that the basis for the analysis could be cost per pound of composite prepreg produced.

The energy costs were based on the current measurements of energy usage for the laboratory prototype. It was also assumed that 30% of the material would be lost in the production of the prepreg and that one person could run the entire system. Figure 4 shows that the major costs associated with running this process are in the amount of labor required to produce the composite prepreg.

The entire non-material cost is \$12.12 per pound. This figure is not unexpectedly high considering the analysis was completed on the laboratory prototype. Reasonable extrapolations were made as to the ability to increase the size, speed, capacity while reducing the amount of operator attention required. The operating conditions for the scaled-up version using 150,000 fibers (i.e. 50, 3K tows or 12.5, 12K tows) at a speed of 10 cm/sec with one operator reduced the non-material cost of the process to \$2.99 per pound.

The interplay between prepregging speed and the number of systems that could be monitored by one operator is a very important factor in predicting costs. Figure 5 shows that combined dependence of this process on these factors. It is interesting to note that the non-material cost of operating this process approach \$1.00 per pound at two speeds of 30 cm/sec, a one operator running three prepregging lines at only 25,000 pounds per year throughput. While these figures are extrapolations, they are based on reasonable extensions from data obtained on the laboratory

prototype.

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Dry powder impregnation to form flexible prepreg tapes is a generic process which can be used to prepreg fibrous reinforcements with any thermoplastic or thermoset matrix that is available in particle form. The relative dimensions of the fiber and the thermoplastic powder particles are the main parameters which decide the uniformity of the prepreg tapes. The key elements of a controllable process are the use of fine particles roughly of the order of dimensions of the reinforcing fiber, an impregnation chamber which delivers a controlled concentration of particles to the fiber tow and the ability to spread fiber tows so that individual fibers are exposed. The formation of uniform droplets on fiber surfaces in the prepreg tapes and the lack of solvents or chemical reactions during consolidation obviates the need to develop complex processing cycles to make void-free composite parts. The uniform wetting achieved in the coalescence step during prepreg manufacture means that an optimum pressure for constant temperatures and contact times is all that is needed in order to develop consolidation cycles for thermoplastic composites. This process to make flexible prepreg tapes with any desired volume fraction of fiber and matrix has been shown to produce prepreg tapes that can be used in other composite forming operations.

Economic analysis of this process for reasonable scaled-up versions of the laboratory prototype have indicated that the incremental manufacturing costs for using this process are less than \$1.00 per pound at volumes of 25,000 pounds per year.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: The authors wish to acknowledge the financial support of MSU Department of Chemical Engineering, Composite Materials and Structures Center and Michigan Materials and Processing Institute.

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Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the powder-prepreg process

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the stages through which the powder particles progress with increasing residence time in the heater.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the impregnated and spread tow as it passes through the heater.

Figure 4. Percentage breakdown of non-material manufacturing costs per pound of prepreg produced with the laboratory model and manufacturing prototype.

Figure 5. Non-material manufacturing costs per pound of prepreg produced as a function of process speed and operator efficiency.